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MODELS AND ALGORITHMS FOR ASSESSMENT OF RISK SITUATIONS BASED ON FUZZY COLLECTION AND LOGIC

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Abstract: This article covers the issues of fuzzy set and logic-based risk assessment, software product development evaluation, analysis, and wide coverage of their models and algorithms. In addition, in order to improve the efficiency of software products developed in the field of intelligent data analysis, we will also talk about the efforts being made to improve the modules for comparing objects described by various types of symbols, including fuzzy sets, and to develop modified algorithms for identifying symbols. the data explains.

Keywords: Fuzzy set, logic, system, model, algorithm, software, risk, object, information, technical tool.

As we all know, in today's developing age, these techniques and technologies are developing rapidly. It would not be wrong to say that all the comforts for mankind have been created and that the age of technology and equipment is coming. In our country, as the volume of information about processes and events in various aspects of human activity increases dramatically, great attention is paid to the development and improvement of systems for their intellectual analysis. Currently, in order to develop information and communication technologies in our republic, special attention is paid to developing software products, ensuring their security, creating a data center for data processing and storage, and their implementation. In this direction, software products designed for data storage, digital processing, and intellectual analysis of large volumes of information (images, signals, sounds, and video) are being developed. . In addition, in order to improve the efficiency of the software products being developed in the field of intelligent data analysis, it is required to improve the modules for comparing objects described by various types of symbols, including fuzzy sets, and to develop modified algorithms for identifying symbols. Through the use of methods and algorithms developed on the basis of the theory of fuzzy sets

in intelligent systems, "Meeting of robotic devices among people has become commonplace, and according to the research of the International Federation of Robotics in 2017, in 2016, about 1.5 million robots worked in the world. by the end of 2017, their number will increase to 1.9 million." In this regard, the work carried out in the world's leading foreign countries, including the USA, Japan, Germany, Great Britain, Russia, Azerbaijan, and Uzbekistan, on the implementation of the theory of fuzzy sets, is of great importance.[<https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/fuzzy-logic-theory-and-properties>]. The word and concept of algorithm is inextricably linked with the name of the great scholar Abu Abdullah Muhammad ibn Musa al-Khorazmi (783-850), who lived and created in the 9th century. The word "algorithm" comes from the corruption of the name of al-Khorazmi by European scientists. Al-Khorazmi was the first to explain the principles of the decimal number system and the rules for performing the four actions in it in his treatise "Al-kitab al-mukhtasar fi lis al-jabr wa almuqabala" dedicated to arithmetic. And the name of the scientist "al-Khorazmi" has been fixed forever in science in the form of "algorithm". Each instruction or command in an algorithm is intended to perform an action. An object that performs actions in an algorithm can be called an executor. Any algorithm is a rule that determines actions, and as a result of its chain, the desired result comes from the given values. Such a chain of actions is an algorithmic process, and each action with a common aspect in the algorithm is called a step of the algorithm. and we call them programming languages. An algorithmic language is a system of notations and rules used to write algorithms uniformly and precisely. Algorithmic language is close to ordinary language, which includes mathematical symbols (as mentioned above). Algorithms created to solve the given problems cannot be directly entered into the machine and solved, therefore it is necessary to transfer the written algorithm to some algorithmic language. Any algorithmic language has its field of application. Usually, the writing of an algorithm in a language that a computer can understand is called a program. A language that a computer understands is called a programming language. There are thousands of programming languages in the world and their number is growing. Nowadays Pascal, Delphi, C, C++, Java, Python programming languages are common and easy to learn. The main goal of the methods of describing the algorithms seen above is to determine the most convenient situation of the sequence of actions necessary to solve the given problem and to make it easier for a person to write a program. In fact, the program is another form of the algorithm, which is designed to make communication between a person and a computer more convenient. In the Strategy of Actions for further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021, including "Further development of information and communication technologies, creation of more favorable organizational, technological and economic conditions for software product manufacturers, introduction of information and communication technologies to the economy, social sphere and management system implementation" tasks are defined. Implementation of these tasks, including intellectual analysis of data.

The development of recognition algorithms using the elements of fuzzy set theory for systems is one of the important issues. It should be noted that a linguistic variable is a linguistic variable that takes a value from a set of words or phrases of any natural or artificial language. The set of available values of a linguistic variable is called a term-set. It is more natural for humans to give value through words rather than using numbers. Every day we make decisions based on linguistic information such as "very high temperature", "long journey", "quick response", "beautiful bouquet". According to psychologists, a total amount of information is recoded and stored in the form of linguistic terms in the human brain. The concept of linguistic variables is important in fuzzy logic inference and inference-based decision making.

Among the various rules that we encounter every day and every hour in our life, the rules that require the sequential execution of actions leading to the achievement of a necessary result are expressed by the word algorithm, one of the main concepts of informatics. Most algorithms become habits because they are performed many times during a person's life. For example, cooking, eating, dressing properly, leaving the room, writing, going from one place to another, etc. So, a sequence of a finite number of instructions or commands (actions) is an algorithm, and the person executing these algorithms is the executor. The role of the executor of the algorithm is performed by nature, a person, an automated device (computer, technology, robot) and others. If a technical tool is used to solve a problem, the sequence of commands or instructions should be clear and understandable. The more clear and understandable the sequence of commands or instructions, the faster and more precisely the result can be achieved. It is also worth saying that we assume that Logical Reasoning accepts not two values of truth, but three, for example: "true", "false" and "uncertain". In this case, we are dealing with three-valued logic, not two-valued. The total number of binary operations and direct truth tables in three-valued logic is $3^3 = 27$. Fuzzy logic is a form of multi-valued logic in which the truth value is given by terms of linguistic variables or "true" linguistic variables. Rules for performing fuzzy logical operations are formed based on the principle of generalization from logical boolean operations. We denote the fuzzy logical variables by $A \sim$ and $B \sim$, and the relevance functions that give the truth value of these variables by $\sim(u) A$ and $\sim(u) B$, $u \in [0,1]$. AND ($\wedge$), OR ($\vee$), NEGATION ($\neg$) and implication ($\rightarrow$) fuzzy logical operations are performed based on the following rules. In multivalued logic, logical operations can be represented by truth tables. Fuzzy logic can have an infinite number of truth values, which means that it is generally impossible to represent logical operations in tabular form. But in tabular form, representing fuzzy logic operations for finite truth values, such as the term sets {"true", "very true", "not true", "somewhat true", "false"} possible. L. Zade proposed the following linguistic truth tables for the fuzzy three-valued logic of truth - T - "true", F - "false" and T+F - "unknown". In multivalued logic, logical operations can be represented by truth tables. Fuzzy logic can have an infinite number of truth values, which means that it is generally impossible to represent logical operations in tabular form. But in tabular form, representing fuzzy logic operations for finite truth values, such as the term sets {"true", "very true", "not true", "somewhat true", "false"} possible. In conclusion, it can be said that not only in Uzbekistan, but in the whole world, the practice is directed to the development and improvement of modern methods with a "natural" approach working on fuzzy sets in areas that rely on human intelligence, such as intellectual analysis of data, identification of symbols. scientific research is being carried out. In this regard, special attention is being paid to the development and improvement of recognition methods using elements of the theory of fuzzy sets, including heuristic algorithms for character recognition based on the principle of partial precedent. At the same time, we hope that the scientific research conducted by our scientists in this field will definitely help in achieving good results for the development of the field and science in the future.

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